

Studies on interaction of molybdenum(VI) with modified lignocellulosics using a novel spectrophotometric method

M. K. Sreedhar^{a*}, T. S. Anirudhan^b, T. J. John^a and R. Remya^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University College, Thiruvananthapuram-695 034, Kerala, India

E-mail : drmkdsdharuc@hotmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram-695 581, Kerala, India

Manuscript received 23 April 2008, revised 16 December 2008, accepted 19 December 2008

Abstract : A new adsorbent (PGPEP-COOH) bearing carboxylate functional group was prepared through graft co-polymerization of acrylic acid onto pulverized *Phyllanthus emblica* planks using ferrous sulphate/H₂O₂ redox initiator system. The adsorbent obtained was tested for the uptake of molybdenum(VI) from aqueous solutions. The efficiency of the PGPEP-COOH to remove Mo^{VI} ions at different time of contact, initial adsorbate concentration, adsorbent dose, pH, ionic strength and temperature was studied by batch experiments. The amount of molybdenum(VI) in aqueous system was determined using a very simple and sensitive method of estimation using potassium hexacyanoferrate(II). Reddish brown solution of the molybdenum complex at pH 3.2 shows absorption maximum at 390 nm. To establish the most appropriate correlation for adsorption equilibrium, isotherm studies were performed using Langmuir, Freundlich and Redlich-Peterson models. The suitability of isotherm models was compared using linear least square fitting. Experimental kinetic data were described using a diffusion controlled first order reversible model and diffusion coefficient was evaluated at different temperatures. Applying Eyring equation thermodynamic parameters were calculated. PGPEP-COOH adsorbed 99.2% Mo^{VI} from a solution of 10 $\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration at 303 K. Desorption and regeneration studies of the adsorbent under different conditions were also studied.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric determination, adsorption, molybdenum, isotherm, lignocellulose.

Introduction

Water is the most important constituent in the biosphere because on one hand it is vital for the maintenance of all forms of life and on the other hand it helps in the movement, circulation and cycling of nutrients in the biosphere. Molybdenum, an essential trace element functions as a cofactor for a number of enzymes that catalyze important chemical transformations in the global carbon, nitrogen and sulphur cycles¹. But molybdenum excess is associated with adverse health outcomes in healthy people. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a maximum level of 0.07 mg dm⁻³ molybdenum in drinking water². In areas near mining sites, molybdenum concentrations up to 0.2 mg dm⁻³ have been reported. Industries of molybdenum based pigments, paints, lubricants and various other chemicals produce molybdenum rich effluents capable of polluting landmass and water bodies. Food or water that contains more than 100 mg kg⁻¹ molybdenum produce signs of toxicity, which include anaemia, anorexia, diarrhoea, joint abnormalities, os-

teoporosis, hair discoloration, reduced sexual activity and death. Unlike organic pollutants heavy metals are refractory and cannot be degraded and detoxified biologically. Among various available technologies for water pollution control, adsorption process is considered better as compared to other methods because of convenience, easy operation and simplicity of design^{3,4}. Lignocellulose based surface modified biomaterials are effective adsorbents because they contain stable polyphenolic compounds which have high affinity for heavy metal ions⁵. *Phyllanthus emblica* plank (PEP) is a natural lignocellulosic material, which is recognized to be an efficient adsorbent to purify water. The behaviour of its various components individually and in association with others is of primary consideration for the traditional practice to keep the planks at the bottom of the open wells to get clear potable water. The timber consists of large molecular mass lignin linked to cellulose through hemicellulose and occurs as microfibrils⁶. In the present work, pulverized PEP was used as the precursor material for the prepa-

ration of a new adsorbent with -COOH functionality through graft copolymerization of acrylic acid to get PGPEP-COOH for the effective removal of Mo^{VI} from aqueous solutions.

Results and discussion

FTIR spectrum of polymer grafted *Phyllanthus emblica* planks (PGPEP-COOH) shows an asymmetric absorption band at 3323 cm⁻¹ which is due to the sum of contributions of exchangeable O-H groups from alcoholic and phenolic components⁷. The strong band at 2884 cm⁻¹ is due to O-H stretching vibrations of inter and intra molecular H-bonding in cellulose/hemicellulose/lignin making the entire structure as a net work chelate (Table 1). The absorption band observed at 1743 cm⁻¹ represent >C=O stretching vibration. The broad peak at 1232 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C-O stretching band of the carboxylic group. The values of apparent density, moisture content, ash content, cation exchange capacity and surface area are : 1.23 g cm⁻³, 2.5%, 2.1%, 0.93 meq g⁻¹ and 1.87 m² g⁻¹ respectively.

Table 1. Functional group assignment of PGPEP-COOH

Absorbance (cm ⁻¹)	Possible assignments
3323	Exchangeable O-H groups (alcoholic and phenolic)
2884	O-H Stretching vibrations of inter and intra molecular H-bonding
1743	>C=O Stretching vibration
1591	Hydrogen bonded carbonyl group
1507	Aromatic stretching vibration of lignin component
1232	vC-O Stretching of carboxylic group
897	β-Glucosidic linkage
623	Tortional vibration of pyranose ring

Impact of pH on adsorption : The uptake of the metal ions is highly influenced by pH, which affect the surface charge of the sorbent and speciation of the sorbate. The impact of pH of the medium in the adsorption of Mo^{VI} onto PGPEP-COOH was carried out over the pH range 2.0-7.0 (Fig. 1).

A maximum adsorption of 99.2 and 94.7% occurs at an initial adsorbate concentration of 10.0 and 25.0 μmol dm⁻³, respectively at pH 4. In all cases it was observed that the final pH was less than initial pH, which indicates that when Mo^{VI} ions are bound to the substrate, H⁺ ions are released into the solution. This leads to the conclusion that PGPEP-COOH acts as an acid form ion-ex-

Fig. 1. Effect of pH in the removal of Mo^{VI} by PGPEP-COOH.

changer, as indicated by Deshkar *et al.*⁸ for *Hardwickia binata* bark.

Adsorption kinetics : Sorption kinetics and sorption equilibrium are the important physico-chemical aspects used to define the type of adsorption and its evaluation. To model the metal ion adsorption and to determine the rate constants based on batch adsorption data, a simple diffusion controlled first-order reversible kinetic model as previously described by Bhattacharya and Venkobachar⁹ is used. In a rapidly stirred batch reactor, the adsorbate species are most probably transported from the solution to the solid phase through intraparticle transport, which is often the rate-limiting step. Diffusion constant, D_i is related to the fraction of metal adsorbed, X_A at any time as

$$1 - \frac{X_A}{X_{Ae}} = \frac{6}{\Pi^2} \exp \left[\frac{-\Pi^2 D_i}{r^2} \right] t \quad (1)$$

where X_{Ae} is the fraction of the molybdenum adsorbed at equilibrium and r is the particle radius. The straight line plots of $\ln [1 - (X_A/X_{Ae})]$ versus t for PGPEP-COOH for the initial Mo^{VI} concentration of 300.0 μmol dm⁻³ at different temperatures (Fig. 2) indicate the validity of first-order reversible kinetics for the present system. As Weber¹⁰ stated, the rate of sorption will increase with increase in temperature when intraparticle diffusion is acting as the governing factor in the adsorption process. For the increase in temperature from 303 to 333 K the D_i values increased from 5.23×10^{-12} to 6.29×10^{-12} m² s⁻¹ for the initial concentration of 300.0 μmol dm⁻³.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln(X_A/X_{Ae})$ versus t for Mo^{VI} adsorption onto PGPEP-COOH.

Evaluation of thermodynamic parameters : The thermodynamic parameter Gibb's free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger), which represents the driving power for the reaction is determined from equilibrium constant, K_c as,

$$\ln K_c = -\frac{\Delta G^\ddagger}{RT} \quad (2)$$

The other thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy of adsorption (ΔH^\ddagger) and entropy of adsorption (ΔS^\ddagger) for the process were determined by applying Eyring equation, which gives the specific reaction rate for a chemical reaction in terms of the heat of activation, entropy of activation, the temperature and other constants (D_i , k_b , R and h),

$$\ln \left(\frac{D_i}{T} \right) = \left[\ln \left(\frac{k_b}{h} \right) + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R} \right] - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{RT} \quad (3)$$

where D_i is the diffusion coefficient, k_b is Boltzmann constant and h is Planck's constant. The value of ΔH^\ddagger for Mo^{VI} adsorption onto PGPEP-COOH was found to be $22.15 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 2). The positive value of ΔH^\ddagger suggests that the adsorption of metal ions onto PGPEP-COOH is an endothermic process. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger indicate greater order of reaction during the adsorption process. The negative values of ΔG^\ddagger indicate the spontaneous nature of reaction. The increase in negative value with rise in temperature indicates that more adsorption takes place at higher temperature.

Table 2. Diffusion coefficient and thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of Mo^{VI} onto PGPEP-COOH

Temp. (K)	$D_i \times 10^{-12}$ ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	K_c
303	5.23	-3.469	22.15	-453.7	0.252
313	5.47	-3.472	-	-	0.263
323	5.66	-3.477	-	-	0.274
333	6.29	-3.506	-	-	0.282

Equilibrium adsorption isotherm studies : The equilibrium data for the adsorption of Mo^{VI} in the concentration range $100\text{--}800 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ by PGPEP-COOH at different temperatures were analyzed using the Langmuir model to evaluate the mechanistic parameters associated with the adsorption process using the linear form of the Langmuir isotherm equation,

$$\frac{1}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{C_e b Q^0} + \frac{1}{Q^0} \quad (4)$$

where Q_e is the quantity of Mo^{VI} adsorbed at equilibrium ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$), C_e is the aqueous phase Mo^{VI} concentration at equilibrium ($\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$), Q^0 is the maximum adsorption capacity ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$) and b is a constant related to the affinity of binding sites ($\text{dm}^3 \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$). The straight line plots of $(1/Q_e)$ versus $(1/C_e)$ for PGPEP-COOH/ Mo^{VI} system at different temperatures show the validity of the Langmuir isotherm model (Fig. 3). The adsorption parameters Q^0 and b were calculated from the slope and

Fig. 3. Langmuir plots for the adsorption of molybdenum on PGPEP-COOH.

Table 3. Langmuir, Freundlich and Redlich-Peterson isotherm constants for Mo^{VI} adsorption on PGPEP-COOH

Temp. (K)	303	313	323	333
Langmuir constants :	:	:	:	:
Q^o ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$)	469.48	529.10	540.54	549.45
b ($\text{dm}^3 \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$)	2.85×10^{-3}	2.92×10^{-3}	3.20×10^{-3}	3.95×10^{-3}
R^2	0.999	0.999	0.994	0.997
Freundlich constants :				
K_F	2.69	3.45	4.63	5.41
$1/n$	0.784	0.757	0.715	0.713
R^2	0.986	0.988	0.964	0.976
Redlich-Peterson constants :				
α ($\text{dm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$)	3.179	3.977	4.973	6.817
β ($\text{dm}^3 \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$)	1.44×10^{-2}	3.98×10^{-2}	2.96×10^{-2}	2.74×10^{-2}
γ	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.95
R^2	0.990	0.995	0.994	0.979

intercept of the plot and are furnished in Table 3. In all cases the values of the correlation coefficient (R^2) for the linear regression fits were found to be >0.99 . The values of Q^o were increased from 469.48 to 549.45 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, when the temperature increased from 303 to 333 K and the corresponding b values increased from 2.85×10^{-3} to $3.95 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$. The equilibrium data have also been processed according to the Freundlich isotherm model,

$$\ln Q_e = \ln K_F + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e \quad (5)$$

where, K_F and $1/n$ are Freundlich constants representing all factors affecting the adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity respectively. The straight line plots $\ln Q_e$ versus $\ln C_e$ for PGPEP-COOH/Mo^{VI} system at different temperatures show the validity of the Freundlich isotherm model (Fig. 4). It is observed that the K_F values were increased with increase in temperature and values of $1/n$ lie between 0.1 and 1.0 which shows favourable adsorption and the values of R^2 range from 0.988 to 0.964 (Table 3). The three parameter Redlich-Peterson isotherm model was also applied to process the equilibrium data using the following linear equation,

$$\ln \left[\alpha \frac{C_e}{Q_e} - 1 \right] = \ln \beta + \gamma \ln C_e \quad (6)$$

The isotherm constants α ($\text{dm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$), β ($\text{dm}^3 \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$) and γ , the heterogeneity factor, which is a dimensionless constant were computed and optimized values of constants obtained by using linear least square fitting are shown in

Fig. 4. Freundlich adsorption isotherms of Mo^{VI} on PGPEP-COOH.

Table 3. The Redlich-Peterson isotherm model combines the elements from both Langmuir and Freundlich equations and the mechanism of adsorption is a hybrid one and does not follow ideal monolayer adsorption. This equation is thus a compromise between Langmuir and Freundlich systems. The straight line plots of $\ln \left[\alpha \frac{C_e}{Q_e} - 1 \right]$ versus $\ln C_e$ for PGPEP-COOH/Mo^{VI} system at different temperatures show the validity of the Redlich-Peterson isotherm model (Fig. 5). The values of R^2 range from 0.990 to 0.979 indicating a good fit

of the observed data. Present data shows that the heterogeneity factor γ is nearly equal to unity and when $\gamma = 1$, this equation gets reduced to Langmuir isotherm. The values of linear least square fit shows that among the three isotherm models, Langmuir model is the best fit at all temperatures. The correlation coefficient obtained for Redlich-Peterson isotherm model is greater than that of Freundlich isotherm model but less than that of Langmuir isotherm model.

Fig. 5. Redlich-Peterson isotherm plots of Mo^{VI} adsorption on PGPEP-COOH.

Desorption and regeneration : Extraction studies of metal loaded PGPEP-COOH with 0.10 and 0.25 M solutions of CH_3COOH , NaNO_3 , $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, Na_2SO_4 , HCl , HNO_3 and EDTA were conducted and found that 0.25 M HCl is the best extractant. The adsorbent desorbed 98.9% of the adsorbed metal ions in the first cycle and the percentage desorption decreased to 96.7% in the second cycle and to 94.1% in the third one. Hence PGPEP-COOH is a good reusable adsorbent.

Spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} : The reaction of molybdenum with potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) gives a reddish brown soluble complex in iron-free HCl medium at room temperature. This complex shows a maximum absorption at 390 nm against a reagent blank at pH 3.2. No interferences were observed with Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , but V^{V} and W^{VI} affected the complex formation. However, the complex was very stable and observations are in good agreement with Beer's law up to

$20.0 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ with an excellent linearity in terms of correlation coefficient value >0.996 . This simple and sensitive reaction is used for the spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} . Molar extinction coefficient was calculated and found to be $1.67 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The stoichiometry of molybdenum-hexacyanoferrate(II) complex is determined by the method of continuous variation called Job's method¹¹. Keeping the total number of moles of ligand and metal ions same, a series of solutions were prepared by mixing the required quantity of reagents in HCl medium at room temperature for the complex formation. The concentration of the complex formed was determined spectrophotometrically. In each mixture either the metal or the ligand will act as the limiting reagent. The reaction was monitored at 390 nm. In the plot (Fig. 6) of absorbance versus the mole fraction of the ligand (X_L), the two linear branches intersected. The point of intersection corresponds to the X_L value of 0.86. The value of Y in the complex ML_Y is evaluated from the

Fig. 6. Plot of absorbance versus X_L for the complex of Mo^{VI} and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$.

following equation and found that the metal to ligand ratio in the complex is 1 : 6.

$$Y = \frac{X_L}{1 - X_L} \quad (7)$$

Experimental

Finely pulverized *Phyllanthus emblica* planks of aver-

age particle size 0.096 mm were the precursor material which was subjected to graft polymerization by acrylic acid after copper impregnation. Dried impregnated sample was treated with redox couple¹² of 4×10^{-4} M ferrous sulphate, 6×10^{-3} M H_2O_2 and 0.1 M acrylic acid. Mo_2O_3 was treated with iron free hydrochloric acid and diluted to get Mo^{VI} solution of desired concentration. The metal removal was evaluated under a wide range of conditions such as contact time, pH, initial Mo^{VI} concentration, adsorbent dose, ionic strength and temperature. Kinetic experiments were carried out with an initial concentration of $300.0 \mu mol dm^{-3}$ at different temperatures at pH 4.0 with $2.0 g dm^{-3}$ sorbent concentration. The kinetics of Mo^{VI} was modeled as described by Bhattacharya and Venkobachar. The values of diffusion coefficient, D_i and equilibrium constant, K_c were determined and using these values the thermodynamic parameters such as free energy of activation, enthalpy and entropy of adsorption were calculated applying Eyring equation. The equilibrium data of Mo^{VI} adsorption was analysed using Langmuir, Freundlich and Redlich-Peterson isotherm models and the different parameters were determined. Metal loaded PGPEP-COOH was treated with acids, salt solutions and complexing agents to regenerate the adsorbent. Spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} with potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) at pH 3.2 was used to measure the metal ion concentration.

Conclusions :

A novel adsorbent PGPEP-COOH was developed with carboxylate functionality through graft polymerization of acrylic acid onto pulverized *Phyllanthus emblica* planks with Fenton's reagent¹³ ($Fe^{2+} + H_2O_2$) as an initiator where Ferric/Ferrous interconversion in a single step one electron transfer process occurs. The concentration of Mo^{VI} in aqueous solutions can be measured using spectrophotometric method developed based on reaction between Mo^{VI} and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) in acid medium. The removal capacity of PGPEP-COOH for Mo^{VI} ions from aqueous solution was maximum at pH 4.0. The adsorption kinetic data is well described by diffusion con-

trolled first-order reversible kinetic model. The Langmuir model was the best fit to the equilibrium data over the entire concentration and temperature range studied. From the adsorbed sample the metal ions can be extracted with 0.25 M HCl and the regenerated adsorbent is found to be reusable.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, University College, Thiruvananthapuram for providing necessary laboratory facilities and we wish to express our sincere gratitude to University Grants Commission for providing the financial assistance for this investigation.

References

1. H. A. Schroeder and M. Mitchener, *Archives of Environmental Health*, 1971, **23**, 102.
2. WHO, Guidelines for drinking water quality, ed. II, World Health Organisation, Geneva, 1993.
3. M. K. Sreedhar, T. S. Anirudhan, N. S. Smitha and Divya S. Nair, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 770.
4. V. C. Srivastava, I. D. Mall and I. M. Mishra, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **134**, 257.
5. D. Mohan and K. P. Singh, *Wat. Res.*, 2002, **36**, 2304.
6. C. T. Brett and K. W. Waldron, "Physiology and Biochemistry of Plant Cell Walls", ed. II, Chapman and Hall, 2-6 Boundary Row, London, 1996.
7. K. Nakanishi and P. H. Solomon, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Holden Day, Inc. San Francisco, 1977
8. A. M. Deshkar, S. S. Bokode and S. S. Dara, *Wat Res.*, 1990, **24**, 1011.
9. A. K. Bhattacharya and C. Venkobachar, *J. Environ. Engg.*, 1984, **110**, 110.
10. W. J. Weber (Jr.), "Sorption from Solution by Peat Carbon", In : 'Principles and applications of water chemistry', eds. S. D. Faust and J. V. Hunter, Wiley, New York, 1967.
11. David Harvey, "Modern Analytical Chemistry", McGraw Hill International Edition, Singapore, 2000.
12. M. K. Sreedhar and T. S. Anirudhan, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2000, **75**, 1261.
13. P. Chowdhary, A. Ali, T. Kundu and A. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 88.